

High Temperature Fatigue Behavior of SiC Fiber Reinforced Aluminum

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ABSTRACT

Polycrystalline β -SiC fiber has good high tensile strength & compatibility, and is well suited for the reinforcing of aluminum. During high temperature cyclic loading, composite degrades in a complex way. This paper will present the result of experimental investigation of the high temperature static & dynamic mechanical properties of SiC/Al composites.

Composites were made by modified Liquid Metal Pressing Method. Results on composites with various fiber orientations, stacking sequences, fibre-vol. fraction and relationship between the tensile fatigue properties and environmental temperature were investigated and presented. From the results the dynamic mechanical responses and fatigue controlling factor of the composites at high temperature can be obtained.

The fatigue properties is dependent upon the environmental temperature significantly, and the contribution of the reinforcing phase at high temperature is different from at low temperature. Details will be explained with macro- and microscopic basis.

Key Word

FRM, SiC/Al, Fabrication, Liquid metal pressing, Microstructure, Fracture surface, Dynamic properties at elevated temperature.

